

On the identity of the poorly known spider species *Centromerus obscurus* Boesenberg, 1902 and description of a new species (Araneae: Linyphiidae)

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Abstract: The taxonomic status and distribution of the poorly known linyphiid species *Centromerus obscurus* Boesenberg, 1902 is discussed on the basis of newly collected material from Bulgaria. Additionally, after a review of the related literature and the newly collected material, a new species of *Centromerus* species, *C. thaleri* **sp. n.**, is described based on both sexes and *Centromerus obscurus* is considered **nomen dubium stat. reconf.**

Keywords: Bulgaria, discussion, new records, taxonomy

Introduction

The identity of *Centromerus obscurus* Bösenberg, 1902, described only based on two females from Germany in the early 20th century, remains unclear. As the type is unfortunately lost (Renner, 1988), the only evidence available to interpret the identity of this taxon is Bösenberg’s original description and illustrations, as well as scarce and contradictory follow-up reports (Roewer, 1928 and other sources listed in Braun, 1982), as well as the regional faunal surveys near the locus typicus (Arachnologische Gesellschaft, 2025). This was the reason the species was considered nomen dubium by Braun (1982) but was soon revalidated by Thaler (1983) who claimed to have found one female in Austria. Thaler himself was uncertain about the identification, commenting on the morphological differences between his specimen and the original description, thus adding a question mark.

Finding what appears to be Thaler’s species in Western Bulgaria by the second author (see Material in the Results section below), including the

previously unknown male, revived the discussion. While morphologically identical to Thaler’s species apart from the colouration (see description), this finding prompted a reevaluation of the actual identity of Bösenberg’s taxon with the help of the available literature. The aim of the present publication is to clarify the relationship between the new findings and *Centromerus obscurus* using the available literature and to describe the collected species as new.

Material and methods

The studied material was collected by hand. Colouration is described from alcohol preserved specimens. Measurements of the legs were taken from the dorsal side and follow the format total length (femur, patella, tibia, metatarsus, tarsus). Total length of the body includes the chelicerae. All measurements are in mm. Specimens were examined and measured using a Wild M5A stereomicroscope. Digital images were taken with a Canon EOS1100 attached to a Carl Zeiss Amplitval microscope and processed using

Adobe Photoshop CS6 software. The specimens are preserved in 70–95% ethanol and deposited in National Museum of Natural History, Sofia (NMNHS) and the personal collection of S. Indzhov (CSI). The nomenclature follows the World Spider Catalog (World Spider Catalog 2026) and the taxa are listed alphabetically.

Abbreviations follow Ballarin & Pantini (2020): ALE = anterior lateral eyes; AME = anterior median eyes; PLE = posterior lateral eyes; PME = posterior median eyes; PLE = posterior lateral eyes; APP = antero-proximal part of the median membrane; CG = copulatory grooves; CO = copulatory opening; DS = distal part of scapus; E = embolus; P = paracymbium; PMP = posterior median plate; R = radix; RA (I-III) = radical apophyses; S = spermatheca; SA = distal suprategular apophysis; TA = terminal apophysis.

Results

Linyphiidae

Centromerus thaleri sp. nov.

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Material. Holotype: ♂ (NMNHS), Bulgaria, Chepan Mt (Dragoman District), 42.9390°N, 22.9495°E, 24.12.2020 (S. Indzhov leg.). Paratypes: 1 ♀ (NMNHS) same data as the holotype; 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (NMNHS) same location as the holotype, 13.11.2023 (S. Indzhov leg.); 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CSI) Balsha Village (Sofia District), 42.8598°N, 23.2599°E, 15.03.2024 (S. Indzhov leg.); 3 ♀♀ (CSI) Balsha Village (Sofia District), 42.8598°N, 23.2599°E, 22.12.2024; 2 ♀♀ (CSI) Aldomirovtsi Village (Sofia District) 42.8968°N, 23.0084°E, 19.02.2024 (S. Indzhov leg.).

Material used for comparison: *Centromerus capucinus* (Simon, 1884), 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ Bulgaria, Chepan Mt (Dragoman District), 13.11.2023 (S. Indzhov leg.).

Diagnosis

The new species is closely related to *C. capucinus* Simon, 1884. The lateral parts of the epigyne are more rounded and broader in *C. thaleri* sp. n., while

being much smaller in *C. capucinus*. The males of *C. capucinus* and *C. thaleri* sp. n. differ mainly by the radical apophyses, being well-separated in *C. thaleri* sp. n. and close together in *C. capucinus* (Figs 1–14).

Etymology

The species name is a patronym dedicated to the well-known arachnologist Konrad Thaler.

Description

Male holotype. Measurements: Total length 2.34; cephalothorax length 1.15, width 0.90; sternum length 0.54, width 0.46; chelicerae length 0.50, width 0.21; clypeus height 0.07; eye diameters: AME 0.05, ALE 0.07, PME 0.05, PLE 0.05; cymbium 0.32; abdomen length 1.26; legs: I – 4.53 (1.22, 0.28, 1.26, 1.08, 0.68); II – 4.17 (1.15, 0.28, 1.11, 1.00, 0.61); III – 3.60 (1.00, 0.21, 0.86, 1.00, 0.50); IV – 4.35 (1.26, 0.28, 1.26, 1.15, 0.68). Colouration (Figs 1–4): Chelicerae yellow-brown, armed with three teeth on outer row and four denticles on inner row. Carapace and sternum, yellow. Abdomen, pale-grey. Legs yellow to pale yellow, femora I with a dorsal and a prolateral spine; femora II-III with 1 dorsal spine; tibiae III-IV with one dorsal spine; tibia IV with one dorsal spine.

Palp (Figs 5, 6, 9–11): Cymbium without distal tubercle. Paracymbium large with slightly jagged inner margin, four short hairs near proximal end. Three radical apophyses, the first well developed, slightly curved and pointed at the end, the second one step-wise wide at the base, then abruptly thinning out and curved at a right angle, third one also well developed, slightly curved and pointed at the end. Distal suprategular apophysis long, slightly curved and robust. Antero-proximal part of median membrane with two rows of teeth, one with small and stumpy teeth and the other with longer and thin teeth. Terminal apophysis transparent and scarcely visible. Embolus massive, curved, pointed apically.

Female (paratype). Measurements: Total length 2.52; cephalothorax length 1.26, width 0.86; sternum length 0.54, width 0.50; chelicerae length 0.50, width 0.22; clypeus 0.07; eye diameters: AME 0.05, ALE 0.07, PME 0.05, PLE 0.05; abdomen 1.51; Legs: I – 4.39 (1.22, 0.28, 1.26, 0.93, 0.68); II – 4.03 (1.15,

Figs 1–4. *Centromerus thaleri* sp. n.: male habitus, dorsal and ventral view (1–2); female body, dorsal and ventral view (3–4). Scale bars – 0.3 mm.

Figs 5–12. *Centromerus thaleri* sp. n.: (5, 6, 9, 10) left male palp, retrolateral/prolateral view; (11) embolic division, prolateral view; (7, 8) Epigyne/vulva, ventral/dorsal view; (12) epigyne. Scale bars – figures 5, 6, 9, 10 – 0.05 mm; figures 7, 8, 12 – 0.06 mm.

Figs 13, 14. *Centromerus thaleri* sp. n.: (13) epigyne, lateral view; (14) vulva, dorsal view. Scale bars – 0.06 mm.

0.28, 1.11, 0.90, 0.57); III – 3.34 (1.00, 0.21, 0.86, 0.79, 0.46); IV – 4.28 (1.26, 0.28, 1.26, 1.08, 0.68).

Colouration as in male.

Epigyne/vulva (Fig. 7, 8, 12–14): Anterior wall triangular, lateral sides rounded and broad. Distal part of scapus wide and rhomboid. Posterior median plate small, curved and rectangular, with a triangular extension in the middle, pointed to distal part. Spermathecae elongated and kidney-shaped. Copulatory ducts turning arcuate posteriorly and outward before returning to the middle part of vulva, ending in copulatory openings in distal part of scapus.

Ecology

The species matures in winter. It inhabits the soil of open, xerothermic habitats and is occasionally found in or near ant nests.

Distribution

Known only from Bulgaria and Austria.

Discussion

Braun (1982) thoroughly examined the available evidence for all species described by Bösenberg and gave his interpretations, although he expressed uncertainty on many of them. Regarding *Centromerus obscurus*, he stated that ‘the epigyne shows with

[some] probability a species which belongs to a member of Microneteae (sensu Wiehle [1956]), with the genera *Agyneta* and *Meioneta* most likely coming in question’. This careful formulation shows that Braun was convinced that the original description of the species did not allow an unambiguous identification, and even expressed doubts about Bösenberg’s generic placement. Braun also discussed Roewer (1928)’s interpretation of *Centromerus obscurus*. According to him, it was ‘surprising that Roewer [1928] this time did not copy the drawing by Bösenberg’, and speculated that Roewer could have examined one of the syntype females. ‘If so,’ he continued, ‘Roewer’s drawing could only originate from a strongly forwards (ventrally) turned epigyne, or the depicted epigyne belongs to a *Centromerus* from the *sylvaticus* group (compare to [...] *C. alnicola* Schenkel [,] 1936, one however much smaller-sized species!).’ *Centromerus alnicola* Schenkel, 1936 is currently considered a synonym of *Centromerus semiater* (L. Koch, 1879) (WSC, 2026). Again, Braun (1982) formulated his interpretation very carefully, in conditionals, in an attempt to explain the discrepancies between the early works. His comments on later findings from the Netherlands and Poland also showed two distinct misidentifications – as *Agyneta saxatilis* (Blackwall, 1844) and as *Centromerus brevipalpus* (Menge, 1866), respectively. These three contradictory interpretations of the identity of *Centromerus obscurus* in the subsequent literature only highlight the inadequacy of this description.

Thaler (1983) added an additional putative species to the list, herein identified as *Centromerus thaleri* sp.

nov. He himself was not convinced of the identification, adding a question mark to the name and mentioning morphological differences between his material and the original description (larger lateral parts of the epigyne than in the description at Bösenberg 1902). We also think we should comment on one other possible candidate for the true identity of *Centromerus obscurus*: *Centromerus capucinus* (Simon, 1884), a species which Bösenberg treated as a member of another genus and knew only from the male sex (Bösenberg, 1901). Specimens of both taxa were collected from the same area of Southwestern Germany, where Bösenberg was active. In present-day Germany, *Centromerus capucinus* has many records from this area (Arachnologische Gesellschaft, 2025), while the species reported by Thaler is yet to be found in this well-surveyed region – its current distribution ranging from Eastern Austria (East of the Alps) to the Balkans. While it is not automatically excluded that our species is found west of the Alps (*Centromerus capucinus* is found across a large part of Europe), it is dubious that German surveying efforts for the last 125 years have failed to find any individuals. Both the morphological discrepancies and the distribution make Thaler (1983)'s interpretation of the taxon likely also incorrect.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Christo Deltchev: conceptualisation, methodology, resources, supervision, visualisation, writing—

original draft, writing—review and editing; Simeon Indzhov: conceptualisation, data curation, investigation, resources, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

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